

**METHODOLOGY OR DEVELOPING 21ST- CENTURY
SKILLS (4K+) THROUGH LITERATURE****Mambetova Gulchekhra Abibullayevna**Senior Lecturer, Department of Language Teaching Methodology,
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18054197>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 23rd December 2025Accepted: 24th December 2025Online: 25th December 2025**KEYWORDS***21st-century skills, 4C+, literature classes, critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, character, citizenship.***ABSTRACT***The article examines the methodology for developing 21st-century skills (4C+) in literature classes, including critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, as well as character development and citizenship. The study highlights the use of interactive and project-based teaching methods to foster analytical thinking, moral values, and social responsibility. The findings are relevant for modern educational practice.*

21st-century education has entered a new stage of human development. The main goal of education at this stage is not to memorize information, but to educate the student as a person who can think independently, creatively, cooperatively, and have civic responsibility. To achieve these results, the foundation of 4K skills in education was laid, and the concept of "21st Century Skills" was formed. This term was first used in the late 1990s as part of educational reforms in the USA and European countries.

1. Initial stage: The emergence of a competency-based approach in education (1990-2000).

In the 1980s, as a result of the development of information technologies, economic globalization, and rapid changes in the labor market, the traditional education system began to fall short of requirements.

During this period, a new concept emerged in pedagogy - "competency." It was interpreted as the unity of knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

In 2002, the Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) in the USA defined the skills of the 21st century in education. The main goal of this organization was to harmonize modern education with the requirements of the labor market.

2. Second stage: Formation of the 4K model concept (2000-2010).

In the program announced by P21 (hereinafter - Battelle for Kids) in 2007, 4 basic competencies were identified as the main goal of education. They are:

1. Critical thinking - analysis of problems, differentiation of arguments and opinions.
2. Creativity - the ability to create new ideas and solutions.
3. Communication - the ability to convey thoughts easily and effectively.
4. Collaboration - the ability to work effectively in a team and share responsibility.

This quadruple has become widespread in global pedagogy under the name "4C Skills" or the "4K model."

Main scientific basis

The 4K model is based on the theory of constructivism (J. Piaget, L. Vygotsky, J. Bruner). According to this theory, knowledge is not presented in a ready-made form; rather, the student creates it through active participation.

Therefore, 4K skills place the student at the center of the educational process - that is, the idea of "learner-centered education" emerges.

3. Third stage: the international application of the 4K model (2010-2020).

Since the 2010s, 4K skills have become an integral part of global educational policy.

The OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) adopted the "Future of Education and Skills 2030" concept in 2018, where 4K skills were defined as the main outcome of education.

UNESCO (2015) combined the "Learning to know, to do, to be, and to live together" concept with 4K in education, aiming to foster active civic engagement, ethical conduct, and social responsibility in every student.

In the PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) assessment system, such skills as "Creative thinking" and "Collaborative problem-solving" have been evaluated separately since 2018.

Thus, 4C has become part of global educational standards not only in theory but also in practice.

4. Fourth stage: 4K+ model - adding the dimension of ethics and citizenship (2020s).

In recent years (2020-2024), the "4K+" or "6C Skills" model has been developing in the field of education. Two more important competencies were added to this model:

Character (Personal qualities, morality) - the formation of human values, responsibility, and inner culture.

Citizenship (Civic consciousness) - social activity in society, awareness of global and national civic values.

This model has been extensively covered by Michael Fullan (Fullan, 2014) and the OECD Education 2030 Framework (2019). According to this, modern education should encompass not only "knowing," but also "being a good person" and "doing socially beneficial work."

The 4K model is a fundamental universal competency system in education, encompassing the following:

Critical thinking - the ability to analyze, evaluate, and distinguish between arguments and opinions.

Creativity means creating a new idea, re-evaluating a work, and expressing one's point of view through artistic expression.

Communication is the development of a culture of correct expression, discussion, and speech.

Collaboration is the ability to work in a group, listen to the opinions of others, and come to a common conclusion.

Two more important elements have been added to this quadruple in recent years:

5. Character (morality, responsibility).

6. Citizenship (civic consciousness and a global perspective).

Thus, the "4K+" educational model is aimed at shaping a person not only as an educated person, but also as a culturally and spiritually developed individual. In developing these skills, literature has broader possibilities compared to other subjects. Literature is an active science that awakens human consciousness and feelings. It teaches the reader to think, evaluate, feel, and draw conclusions.

a) Critical thinking

In the process of analyzing a literary work, students analyze the author's idea, the actions of the characters, and the causes and consequences of the events.

For example, questions like "How do you assess Aydos biy's involvement in the deaths of his two younger brothers, and who is to blame?" regarding T. Qayipbergenov's work "Baxitsizlar" activate critical thinking.

b) Creation.

Students develop creative thinking by creating a new ending based on the plot of the work, writing a letter to the hero, or writing a poem inspired by the work. For example, devising a new ending for M. Nizanov's story "Aqshagúl," that is, concluding it not with the death of the protagonist, but with a different outcome, or the creative essay task "How does the idea of love in Ajiniyoz's works correspond to the present time?" yields good results.

c) Communication

Through group discussions, debates, and essay analysis, students develop their speaking skills and the ability to express their opinions with reasoning. For example, the technique of question-and-answer sessions and interviews between the characters of the work and journalists.

d) Cooperation. (Collaboration)

Through group work, collective analysis, and creative projects, students learn to support each other and perceive the diversity of opinions. For example, "Silent Collaboration," that is, conveying the coherence of the work's content in a group through sequential illustrations without the group members communicating.

e) Character and Citizenship.

Through literature, moral values and national and global civic consciousness are formed. For example, the ideas of humanism, patriotism, and responsibility are vividly reflected in the works of Karakalpak poets and writers.

In general, as a result of teaching literature based on the 4K+ model:

The student becomes a free, thinking, and creative individual.

Skills of teamwork, communication, and critical thinking are formed.

moral and civic values are strengthened.

Thus, 4K skills are the strategic foundation of 21st-century education, shaping students not only as knowledgeable but also as independent, responsible, and creative individuals.

This model is evaluated as a scientific revolution that has shifted education from the center of knowledge to the center of personality.

Literature is the most effective field for the natural development of these skills, and the practical application of the 4K+ model makes it the center of the modern educational paradigm.

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